

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 11

Acceptance of papers **November, 2025**

**Acceptance of
papers**

Published monthly

Topics

economics,
technology, social
sciences

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli – Senior
lecturer at TSUI

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: innovationist2025@gmail.com

The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

Electronic publication, Issue 11. 332 pages.
Approved for publication on November, 2025.

Editorial board:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Cham Tat Huei,
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Muhammad Imran Sadiq
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
Professor, Malaysia

Ahmed Aziz Ismail
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc),
Professor (Egypt)

Lee Chin
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
(Malaysia)

Asongu Simplicé
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
Cameroon

Rui Dang
Doctor of Chemistry (DSc), Professor, China

Zahoor Ahmed
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Turkey

Shujaat Abbas
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Russia

Tina A Coffelt
Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences
(PhD), USA

CONTENTS

POVERTY AND DEVELOPMENT	14
Kholmirezayev Abdulhamid Khapizovich	
WAYS TO ACHIEVE ECONOMIC STABILITY THROUGH THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.....	23
Sadriddinov Bakhtiyor	
STRUCTURE-PROPERTY RELATIONSHIP OF ORGANOSILICON MATERIALS: EVALUATION BASED ON THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS	36
Tosheva Dilfuza Farxodovna, Siddikov Ikrom Iminjonovich, Rakhimov Firuz Fazlidinovich	
"CREATING AN ALGORITHM AND SOFTWARE TOOL FOR PERSONAL IDENTIFICATION USING FACIAL SCANNING TO PROTECT THE OPERATING SYSTEM"	43
Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li	
ENSURING INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION BASED ON MOBILE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES.....	51
Zaripov Olimjan Kuvandiq son	
MONITORING OF THE AYDAR-ARNASAY LAKE SYSTEM AND ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF COLLECTOR WATER INFLOWS INTO THE LAKE ECOSYSTEM.....	55
Erkabayev Furkat Ilyasovich, Madrimov Rajabboy Masharipovich, Aminov Khamza Khusanovich	
APPROBATION OF THE RESISTANCE OF BRICKS MADE FROM "ANGREN" SECONDARY KAOLIN TO THE EFFECT OF LIQUID METAL.....	62
Umurov Ulug'bek Meylievich	
THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PERFORMANCE-BASED BUDGETING.....	68
Allakuliev Akmal Baltayevich	
IMPROVING ECONOMIC MECHANISMS THROUGH EFFECTIVE USE OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS IN TOURISM DEVELOPMENT.....	71
Abdusalomov Djamshid Abdusalomovich	
TEMPERATURE-RADIATION REGIME OF THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN FOR THE DESIGN OF SOLAR GREENHOUSES	76
Ilkhom Ismatovich Rakhmatov, Shakhzod Niyoz ogli Izomov	
THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF GREEN FINANCING IN FORMING A GREEN ECONOMY	81
Khalikov S. X.	
MUVAFFAQIYATLI STARTAP FAOLIYATIDA ROL O'YNOVCHI MUHIM OMILLAR VA O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA STARTAP EKOTIZMINING RIVOJLANISHI.....	87
Qosimova Dilorom Sobirovna	
EFFECTIVENESS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS.....	92
Umarova Nilufar Abdulkakhorkizi	
INFLUENCE OF INTERNATIONAL RANKING ORGANIZATIONS ON HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND EXISTING PLATFORMS	96
Urozboev Khayrulla Murodboy ugli	
BASE STATION MONITORING TECHNOLOGIES IN MOBILE NETWORKS	103
Ibrokhimkhuja Rikhsikhujayev, Mohit Bhandwal	
FORMATION AND MANAGEMENT OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS OF ENTERPRISES	108
Abdunazarov Saidakhmat Abdumalikovich	
THE IMPORTANCE OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN ENTERPRISE ACTIVITY MANAGEMENT.....	113
Rasulov Shavkat Sharof son	
PARTICIPATORY BUDGETING OF THE STATE BUDGET	117
Khamidov Khabibullo Khikmatulla ogli	
TRANSFORMING THE HIGHER EDUCATION SECTOR THROUGH PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP UNDER CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION	123
Abdullayev Javohir Abdumalik og'li	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF THE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN ENTERPRISES.....	131
Begalov Sherzod Maxsutaliyevich	

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE RESERVOIR SAFETY ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE TALIMARJON RESERVOIR.....	136
Xodjaqulova Nodira Xosiyatqul qizi	
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY AND INNOVATIVE TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IMPLEMENTATION IN UZBEKISTAN'S OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY	141
Tarakhtiyeva Gulmira Kulbayevna	
INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO RISK MANAGEMENT AND ASSESSMENT OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	145
Muxitdinova Kamola Alisherovna	
INNOVATIVE COOPERATION AND MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR STRENGTHENING THE REGIONAL ECONOMY: THE CASE OF NAMANGAN REGION	149
Sattarov R. A.	
MARKETING PROBLEMS IN THE INTERNATIONAL TEXTILE MARKET AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN SOLVING THEM.....	159
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
THE PROBLEMS OF LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF ELLIPTICAL SENTENCES IN MODERN ENGLISH.....	165
Jurayeva Hilola Kamol qizi, Eshonkulov Ravshan Tokhironovich	
THE EFFECTIVENESS AND PROSPECTS OF INTEGRATING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INTO URBAN SECURITY DEVELOPMENT	171
Iminov Akbarjon Odiljonovich	
21ST CENTURY CHANGES AND THE GROWING IMPORTANCE OF PROFESSIONAL ENGLISH PROFICIENCY	175
Rakhimova Shirin Utkurovna	
A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF UZBEKISTAN'S INNOVATION EFFICIENCY: EVALUATING GII OUTPUT-INPUT RATIOS RELATIVE TO LEADING AND EMERGING INNOVATIVE ECONOMIES	179
Umidjon Khoshimov	
ANALYSIS OF MODERN FINANCING MODELS FOR OUTSOURCING SERVICES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND THEIR EFFICIENCY	189
Khamidov Anis Choriyevich	
СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ АРХИТЕКТУР ДИАЛОГОВЫХ СИСТЕМ ДЛЯ МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ПРЕДМЕТНОЙ ОБЛАСТИ	195
Гофуржонов Мухаммадали Расулжон угли, Бурханова Айгуль Ильясовна	
EFFICIENT USE OF FINANCIAL RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN'S FORESTRY SECTOR	201
Mamatqulova Muxlisaxon Mamirjanovna	
ESG RISKS AND CORPORATE ACCOUNTABILITY: GLOBAL LESSONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR UZBEKISTAN	206
Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich	
PRACTICE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN PROVIDING FINANCING FOR ENTREPRENEURS' INNOVATIVE INITIATIVE.....	211
Jubanova Bayramgul	
SAMARQAND VILOYATIDA IJTIMOYIY XIZMATLAR SOHASINING RIVOJLANISH DARAJASI VA SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI.....	216
Berdiyeva Nafisa Qahramonovna	
TOURISM SERVICES MANAGEMENT AND IMPROVEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	221
Otaxonova Iroda Xamdamin qizi	
TO'G'RIDAN-TO'G'RI XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALARNING O'ZBEKISTONDA IQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDAGI AHAMIYATI VA UNING DINAMIK TAHLILI	228
Abdurasul A.Sobirov	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA TADBIRKORLIKNI TASHKIL ETISHDA MOLIVAVIY TAVAKKALCHILIKNI BAHOLASH	233
Bayxonov Baxodirjon Tursunbayevich	
ANALYZING N-SHAPED ENERGY VERSUS ENVIRONMENT MODEL: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	240
Xalimjonov Nurbek Ulug'bek o'g'li, Toxirov Shodiyor Zafar o'g'li, Jumamuratov Sultanbek Iyasovich	

PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPING SUSTAINABLE TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN.....	248
Alieva Makhbuba Toychievna	
EXPANDING THE FINANCIAL CAPABILITIES OF LOW-INCOME FAMILIES THROUGH DIGITAL FINANCIAL SERVICES.....	252
Bauyetdinov M.J., Djumamuratova Xurliman	
ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF PUBLIC PROCUREMENT.....	258
Abdurakhmonova Mahliyo Nurmamatovna	
THE IMPACT OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISE FINANCING ON ECONOMIC GROWTH: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	262
Aziza Farmonovna Ergasheva, Rustam Olimjonovich Oltinov	
ANALYSIS OF FACTORS INFLUENCING THE ACTIVITIES OF THE COMPANY'S SALES NETWORK.....	277
Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich	
NODAVLAT OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARINING TIZIMLI RIVOJLANISHIDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	282
Yuldashov Isomiddin Sidiqovich	
LEVERAGING OPEN INNOVATION AND DIGITAL PLATFORMS TO ACCELERATE SUSTAINABLE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM DEVELOPMENT IN EMERGING ECONOMIES.....	288
Azamov Sardor Telman ugli	
PROSPECTS FOR ENSURING BALANCE BETWEEN INDUSTRIAL SECTORS IN THE TERRITORIES OF THE ZARAFSHAN REGION.....	297
Murtazayev Isabek Bazarbayevich	
THE IMPACT OF ECONOMIC GROWTH ON UNEMPLOYMENT IN CENTRAL ASIA.....	306
Kungratov Ilmurod Kuzibay ugli, Jumayev Samariddin Sayfiddin ugli	
EKOTURIZMNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDAGI AHAMIYATI: TABIIY RESURSLARNI MUHOFAZA QILISH VA MAHALLIY HAMJAMIYATLARNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH MASALALARI.....	313
Hamzayeva Dilfuza Samarovna	
THE ESSENCE, IMPORTANCE, AND NECESSITY OF INNOVATION ACTIVITY IN SMALL ENTERPRISES.....	320
Yuldashev Kodirjon Mamadjanovich	
EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF THE ENTERPRISE.....	326
Baymuratova M.M.	

EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF THE ENTERPRISE

Baymuratova M.M.

PhD student at Tashkent

State University of Economics

Abstract: The article examines the need, essence and factors, goals, objectives and problems of managing the financial stability of an enterprise at the present stage of liberalization and modernization of the economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The advantages and features of a creative approach to effective measures of managing the financial stability of an enterprise in the future of the country's socio-economic development have been scientifically substantiated. The possibilities of managing the financial stability of an enterprise in the system of corporate financial management of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been studied and recommendations have been developed.

Key words: corporate finance, corporate financial management, financial stability, financial stability management of the enterprise, assessment of the financial stability of the enterprise, the level of financial stability of the enterprise, indicators of the level of financial stability of the enterprise and the method of them assessment.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida iqtisodiyotni liberallashtirish va modernizatsiya qilishning hozirgi bosqichida korxonaning moliyaviy barqarorligini boshqarish zarurati, mohiyati va omillari, maqsadlari, vazifalari va muammolari o'rganiladi. Mamlakatning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishi kelajagida korxonaning moliyaviy barqarorligini boshqarishning samarali choralariga ijodiy yondashuvning afzalliklari va xususiyatlari ilmiy jihatdan asoslab berilgan. O'zbekiston Respublikasining korporativ moliyaviy boshqaruv tizimida korxonaning moliyaviy barqarorligini boshqarish imkoniyatlari o'rganilgan va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: korporativ moliya, korporativ moliyaviy boshqaruv, moliyaviy barqarorlik, korxonaning moliyaviy barqarorligini boshqarish, korxonaning moliyaviy barqarorligini baholash, korxonaning moliyaviy barqarorlik darajasi, korxonaning moliyaviy barqarorlik darajasi ko'rsatkichlari va ularni baholash usuli.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются необходимость, сущность и факторы, цели, задачи и проблемы управления финансовой устойчивостью предприятия на современном этапе либерализации и модернизации экономики Республики Узбекистан. Научно обоснованы преимущества и особенности креативного подхода к эффективным мерам управления финансовой устойчивостью предприятия в перспективе социально-экономического развития страны. Исследованы возможности управления финансовой устойчивостью предприятия в системе корпоративного финансового менеджмента Республики Узбекистан и разработаны рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: корпоративные финансы, корпоративное финансовое управление, финансовая устойчивость, управление финансовой устойчивостью предприятия, оценка финансовой устойчивости предприятия, уровень финансовой устойчивости предприятия, показатели уровня финансовой устойчивости предприятия и методика их оценки.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in the global economy, as a result of the strengthening of the competitive environment, expansion of the scope of application of financial technologies and innovative development, scientific research is carried out to ensure the formation and effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system. The issues of formation and ensuring the effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system are among the least studied topics in terms of corporate finance, methodology and practice of effective financial management. The issues of formation and ensuring the effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system will help prevent the shadow economy, increase the investment attractiveness of the enterprise. This, in turn, requires conducting scientific research at the international level on a regular basis to ensure the formation and effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system.

In world practice, when conducting a number of studies on the formation and provision of effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system, special attention is paid to the formation and provision

of effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system in both developed and developing countries. Research contributes to the introduction of new types of services at enterprises, improvement of the financial stability of enterprises through venture funds and provision of a competitive market. At present, the conducted studies have not developed scientific proposals and practical recommendations aimed at studying and solving the problems arising in ensuring the formation and effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system, which requires in-depth scientific research in this area. Issues aimed at ensuring the formation and effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system by modernizing investment activities at enterprises, introducing innovative technologies and advanced foreign experience determine the relevance of research work.

The reforms implemented in recent years in the system of formation and ensuring the effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system, in particular, the introduction of effective methods of corporate financial management, the establishment and strengthening of corporate control over the targeted use of enterprise funds, ensuring the openness and transparency of this process, are one of the important issues at the level of state policy.

In conclusion, it can be said that the theoretical, methodological and practical aspects of the formation and provision of effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system in the Republic of Uzbekistan determine the relevance and scientific and practical significance of this scientific article, chosen as a special, independent object of research.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the important characteristics of the activity and development of the production and economic system is its financial stability. Particular importance and necessity of maintaining economic potential are manifested in those cases when “abrupt changes in business conditions and economic situation are observed” [3]. Currently, in economic literature there are various approaches and options for understanding the content of financial stability. In particular, according to I.A. Pavlova, the essence of the financial stability of an enterprise “lies in its financial condition, in which the economic activity of the enterprise allows it to meet all its obligations” [4].

According to I.N. Omelchenko and E.V. Borisova, “financial stability is the ability of an enterprise to maintain its financial stability in the conditions of constant changes in the market situation” [5]. As noted by L.T. Gilyarovskaya and A.A. Vehoreva, “the concept of financial stability of an enterprise lies in the fact that in the process of distribution and use of available resources not only solvency is ensured, but also development is achieved with the aim of achieving profit and capital” [6]. According to E.V. Isaeva, “financial stability of an enterprise is the growth of its financial condition, which has improved compared to the previous one” [7]. According to O.R. Krivitskaya, “financial stability is the presence of a sufficient amount of profit, which is the key to economic independence, significant for the further development of the enterprise [8].”

A generalized analysis of the above opinions showed that there are three approaches to understanding the essence of the concept of “financial stability”. The first approach implies a narrow understanding of this concept and interprets it as one of the indicators of the financial position of an economic entity. Representatives of the second approach, in turn, draw attention to the need to assess the indicators of competitiveness and financial stability, which are a guarantee of the effective implementation of the economic interests of the enterprise and its partners, expressed in the interpretation of the content of this concept. Finally, representatives of the third approach associate the financial stability of an enterprise with the effective formation, distribution and use of financial resources [9].

In our opinion, the financial stability of an enterprise is the ability of an economic entity to finance its activities on an expanded basis, to resist the influence of an unstable external environment and to maintain its solvency even in the most unpleasant situations.

In the conditions of the digital economy, enterprises, although they have great economic opportunities, need state support. In modern conditions, one of the important tasks facing economic science is the development and theoretical substantiation of financial problems of enterprise development, including improving the financial management system of enterprises.

On issues related not only to the system of economic measures, but also to various areas of activity, including the choice of organizational forms and determination of their scale, determination of the development features of enterprises in individual industries, economic analysis and financial condition of enterprises in the digital economy, establishment of financial control on such issues as management of economic and financial activities of enterprises, it is necessary to develop proposals. This is determined by the fact that in new economic conditions, enterprises require a new methodological approach depending on the scale of production, features of economic independence.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The use of scientific observation methods, abstract logical thinking, induction, deduction, statistical, economic, financial analysis, and expert assessment in the research process provides a new approach to effective measures for managing the financial stability of an enterprise.

Analysis and results. In recent years, reforms have been carried out in Uzbekistan in the system of ensuring the formation and effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system, in particular, the introduction of effective methods of corporate financial management, the establishment and strengthening of corporate control over the targeted use of enterprise funds, ensuring the openness and transparency of this process in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Based on the analysis of many financial stability coefficients and for the purpose of a broader reflection of the financial condition of the enterprise, in addition to absolute indicators, to assess the financial stability of enterprises it is necessary to limit ourselves to the following coefficients.

A rational assessment of the financial stability of communications enterprises using absolute and relative indicators of financial stability, given in Table No. 1, is of great importance in the development and implementation of organizational and economic mechanisms for ensuring and increasing the financial stability of enterprises.

1-table. Classification of financial stability coefficients [8].

No.	Coefficient	Formula	Minimum level
1	Absolute liquidity ratio	Cash + Current Investments/Current Liabilities over	2.0 and above (optimal level 0.2 - 0.35)
2	Solvency ratio (current liquidity)	Current Assets/Current Liabilities	2.0 and above
3	Financial independence ratio	Sources of equity/by balance sheet assets	above 0.5 (optimal level 0.65 - 0.75)
4	Debt to equity ratio	Sources of equity/Current liabilities	over 1
5	Ratio of own working capital	Current assets/Sources of equity	over 0.1
6	Accounts receivable turnover ratio	Net sales revenue/Debtors	Max
7	Accounts Payable Turnover Ratio	Net Sales/Accounts Payable	Max
8	Balance Sheet Profit Ratio	Gross profit from sales of products/Net revenue from sales of products	Max
9	Net Profit Ratio	Net profit/Net revenue from sales of products	Max

In general, to ensure the financial stability of enterprises, it is advisable to implement the following measures:

Firstly, in order to increase the level of current liquidity, it is advisable for enterprises to develop a mechanism for purchasing securities using part of their own funds. This allows other enterprises and business entities to pay off their obligations in the form of cash, since securities are quickly sold and converted into cash.

Secondly, investments in the activities of enterprises and the level of their coverage are unstable, and in order to stabilize them, it is advisable to further improve the long-term investment policy of the enterprise.

Thirdly, today enterprises need to increase their ability to finance expanded reproduction, that is, expand production using the profits received, modernize and technically re-equip the enterprise.

Fourthly, to meet their needs at enterprises, it is advisable to use the appropriate resources of the enterprise and external long-term and short-term funds. At the same time, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for the timely repayment of loans received.

Fifthly, in enterprises where the inventory turnover ratio of enterprises is analyzed, they effectively manage their assets today. However, the risks of a shortage of reserves increase here. From this point of view, asset management is advisable to be carried out in combination with reserves.

Sixthly, in order to free enterprises from their obligations, it is advisable to implement an effective system of cashing out working capital. It is also advisable to develop and implement a mechanism for preliminary collection of accounts receivable and sales, converting reserves and costs into finished products.

The system of indicators of the financial condition of enterprises can be divided into two main groups: absolute and relative (Figure 1).

There are a number of absolute indicators that assess the financial condition of an enterprise. These include the solvency of the enterprise, financial stability, the balance of the enterprise or the level of liquidity of assets and a number of other indicators.

As is known, when determining the financial condition of an enterprise, both absolute and relative indicators are widely used.

1-figure. Key indicators of the financial condition of the enterprise¹

A creative approach to managing the financial stability of an enterprise is manifested in the fact that within the framework of the new financial policy in the context of modernization and liberalization of the economy, taking into account the development prospects of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the current tasks of socio-economic development, it is necessary to develop and approve modern trends in the formation and provision of effective operation of the enterprise financial stability management system, the main task is a systematic study and its "financial stability of the enterprise", "factors and means of ensuring financial stability in effective areas of corporate financial management", development of an improved mechanism for harmonization and harmonization of proportions of vital factors, such as "openness of the economy and business environment".

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Financial stability is an integral part of the overall sustainability of the enterprise's development, the availability of funds that allow it to organize its activities over a certain period of time, and the balance of financial flows.

¹ Compiled by the author based on the information he has studied

2. Financial stability is one of the characteristics of the compliance of the composition of sources of financing in the composition of assets. Unlike the solvency indicator, which evaluates the current assets and short-term liabilities of the enterprise, financial stability is determined by the ratio of various sources of financing and their compliance with the composition of the enterprise's assets.

3. The current "Regulations for Conducting Analysis of the Financial and Economic Status of Enterprises with State Participation" provide only one method for calculating the solvency of an enterprise, namely the method for determining absolute solvency, but do not take into account the coefficients of operational and current liquidity. As a result, the financial condition of an enterprise becomes dependent on its hard-to-recover working capital and unlikely accounts receivable, as a result of which economic relations between enterprises turn into a chain of debt obligations. In this regard, in our opinion, it is necessary to include in the current regulatory legal acts the calculation of the coefficients of absolute and current liquidity recommended by international experts.

4. When determining the financial stability coefficient, the method of determining profit in combination with current expenses is recommended. However, this method is aimed at managing expenses, and not at how effectively they are used. Therefore, in our opinion, when calculating efficiency at enterprises, it is advisable to use the profitability indicator of fixed and current assets.

5. To achieve a high level of efficiency of the enterprise production system, the management system must be based on a reasonable, correct strategy based on financial and economic stability. An important component of strategic management of the economic sector will be the analysis of its current activities and assessment of the prospects for further development. Business practice requires improving the methodology for assessing the financial stability of an enterprise in the direction of developing the theory of financial management and, above all, improving the quality of analysis.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated February 7, PF-4947-sonli, 2017.
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Concept of comprehensive socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.
3. Abryutina M.S. "Modern approaches to assessing the financial stability and solvency of a company" / M.S. Abryutina // Financial management. - 2016. - No. 6.-pp.23-27
4. "Analysis and forecasting of the financial stability of an organization taking into account the life cycle based on an integral indicator." I.A. Pavlova // Finance and Credit, 2017, 23 (June), pp. 71-75.
5. Omelchenko I.I. Financial and economic stability as an integral part of the organizational and economic sustainability of enterprises // Bulletin of Mechanical Engineering. 2017. No. 4. P. 65.
6. Gilyarovskaya L.T., Vehoreva A.A. Analysis and assessment of financial stability of a commercial enterprise. St. Petersburg, 2013. P. 13.
7. Isaeva E.V. Problems of defining the essence of the concept of "financial stability of an enterprise" // Problems of Economics. 2018. No. 2. P. 80.
8. Burkhanov A.U.Sanoat korhonalari moliyaviy barkarorligini baholash usuli// "Iktisodiyot va innovative technology" ilmiy electron journal. No. 6, NovemberDecember, 2018
9. Yeletskikh S.Ya. Analysis of theoretical approaches to the interpretation of the essence of the concept of "financial stability of an enterprise" // Economics of industrial development. 2018. No. 1. P. 190.
10. Dzhamalov Kh.N., Urazmetov Zh.M. Tasks of analysis of financial and economic digital activities in the new financial management system//Iktisodiyot va ta'lim, 2021.-№3, pp.96-103

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2025. № 11

© When materials are reproduced, the INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

“The journal “INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY” has been registered by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 09.10.2024 under the registration number №390637. License number: C-5669633. PNFL: 30407832680027

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block,
House 17.

Acceptance of articles
Published every
monthly

Directions
Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

 Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

CERTIFICATE NUMBER: №390637

**ORDER NUMBER ACCORDING TO
THE LICENSE REGISTER: C-5669633**

CONTACT:

 Contact us
+998 50 737 87 88

 Telegram channel
t.me/scopus_IST2100

 Journal official website
<https://ist-journal.uz/index.php/IST>